

A NEW APPROACH SOLVING FOR HYBRID CONSTRAINT SATISFACTION PROBLEMS

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ABSTRACT

In this paper we introduce a new approximate method to solve the Hybrid constraint satisfaction problems (HCSPs), named Hybrid Landmark-based Approximate Inference. HCSPs cannot be deal with computing algebraic systems, since there is not any particular algorithm for common hybrid constraint systems. In addition, splitting and searching techniques for global consistency may incur a huge cost and remain highly complex. Our proposed approach improves the performance and sound results for HCSPs. The main idea of this approach is to generate candidates of landmarks to be utilized during the pruning process to facilitate a quiescent condition of variables in hybrid constraint. The method has been shown to reach not only a local consistency but also a global consistency for complex HCSPs. Besides, it holders complicated problems with a low cost and captures the solutions for various types of hybrid constraints.

KEYWORDS

Approximate reasoning, hybrid constraint satisfaction problems, consistency solutions, global consistency.

1. INTRODUCTION

A Hybrid constraint satisfaction problem (HCSP) is a set of objects, each with an associated domain of possible continuous or discrete values, and set of constraints on these objects [2], [5], [7]. We can transform a real world problem to a HCSP and various frameworks for hybrid constraint systems have been proposed for different purposes in engineering and science such as modeling systems have discrete and continuous changes over time [10], [11], embedded controllers for automobiles [10], simulation industrial mixer system [5]. The real-world application problems are represented by hybrid constraint satisfaction problems such as in [1], [2], [5], [7].

There also are limitations in former algorithms solving for HCSPs such as the time-running increases when we try to find more accurate solutions [2] or focus only on solving local consistency problems for specific types of constraint [5] while the real-world systems are extremely complex systems. The previous methods have not represented clearly the techniques to solve for global consistency solutions of HCSP in possible period running time. Some algorithms have been introduced to solve for HCSPs: Esther Gelle and Boi Faltings [5] solved HCSPs by integrating numeric variables with discrete ones in a single search process. In the algorithm, continuous constraint satisfaction problems are solved using interval methods which create a tree of intervals through bisection, and then intervals are pruned using interval analysis. On the other hand, discrete constraint satisfaction problems are solved by enumerating combinations of variable values. The method only solves for several types of hybrid constraints and returns local consistency solution. Daiske Ishii [2] proposed an interval method for solving of HCSP. The algorithm coordinated interval-based solving of nonlinear ODEs (ordinary differential equations) and a constraint programming technique for reducing interval enclosures of solutions. The method guarantees the existence and uniqueness of a solution in a domain and helps to find the earliest solution reliably. However, the method does not point out global consistency solution and the time for process.

In this paper, we present new algorithms hybrid approximate approach, namely hybrid landmark-based approximate inference to solve for HCSPs. The method uses landmark-based values in constraint propagations to find out not only local consistency but also global consistency solutions of hybrid constraint systems. One approximate mathematical tool is employed to find landmarks propagation for local consistency, and then partitions are found based on the landmarks for global consistency. The key ideas of the method are point and partition landmarks in local and global constraint propagations. The point and partition landmarks which are infeasible will be deleted from the domain of variables and save only feasible values in each iteration of the finding solution process. By generating candidates of landmarks to be utilized during process to facilitate a

quiescent condition, the proposed approach improves the running time and obtains sound results with a low complexity.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 represents some definitions about HCSP. Section 3 gives a framework and properties of our algorithm to find local consistency for hybrid constraint systems. Section 4 discusses how global consistencies for HCSPs get using Hybrid-LAI. The complexity of our algorithm is proved in Section 5. In Section 6 will represent some experimental results after using our method for HCSPs and followed by conclusion in Section 7.

2. PRELIMINARIES

Hybrid Constraint Satisfaction Problem is a network of hybrid constraints which expresses relations among objects by hybrid constraints. HCSP is a decision problem to determine whether there exists a tuple value of all objects which satisfies all hybrid constraints of network. Real world applications of constraint satisfaction problems involve objects with either discrete or continuous domains in the system.

Definition 1 A discrete constraint $\Gamma(X_1, X_2, \dots, X_k)$ defines constraint relations among discrete variables X_1, \dots, X_k in Γ that a set of allowed value tuples $(x_{1,j}, \dots, x_{k,j})$ such that $(x_{1,j}, \dots, x_{k,j}) \in D_1, \dots, D_k$, where $x_{i,j}$ is a value of variable X_i , X_1, \dots, X_k is set of discrete variables have value domains in set of discrete values D_1, \dots, D_k .

This means that domains of variables in constraint system are discrete and finite values. A tuple onto the variables X_1, \dots, X_k will be written $t[X_1, \dots, X_k]$ in which the value of X_i is designated by $t[X_i]$.

In a continuous constraint satisfaction problem, the variable domains are defined over the real numbers or intervals with format $[\alpha, \beta]$, where α, β are real numbers, $\alpha \leq \beta$. A continuous constraint is any relation over the real domain or interval domain. In this paper we use interval domain to represent for continuous domain in the constraints.

Definition 2 A continuous constraint $\Phi(X_1, \dots, X_m)$ is a relation $E \triangleright 0$, where $\triangleright \in \{=, \leq, \geq, >, <\}$ and E is an expression built from constraints, variables, and unary or binary operations $\{+, -, *, /, \exp, \text{sqrt}, \dots\}$ over the real numbers or intervals, X_1, \dots, X_m is set of continuous variables have value domains in set of continuous values D_1, \dots, D_m and the variables $X_i, i=1, \dots, m$ have constraint relations in Φ .

Definition 3 A hybrid constraint $\Omega(X_1, \dots, X_n)$ is a relation defined over the discrete and the continuous variables in set of variables X_1, \dots, X_n of constraint Ω with the each object $X_i, i=1, \dots, n$ in constraint Ω will have discrete domain or continuous domain.

For example the hybrid constraint in Industrial mixer system [5]:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} V = \text{hemispherical} \\ V.\text{volume} = \frac{1}{12} * \pi * V.\text{diameter}^3 + \\ \frac{1}{14} * \pi * V.\text{diameter}^2 * (V.\text{height} - \frac{1}{2} * V.\text{diameter}) \\ V = \text{cylindrical} \\ V.\text{volume} = \frac{1}{14} * \pi * V.\text{diameter}^2 * V.\text{height} \end{array} \right.$$

$$V = \{\text{cylindrical}; \text{elliptical}; \text{hemispherical}\}$$

$$V.\text{volume} = [0.01, 1000]$$

$$V.\text{diameter} = [0.01, 1000]$$

$$V.\text{height} = [0, 1000]$$

Definition 4 A hybrid constraint satisfaction problem (HCSP) is a triple (D, X, C) , where D is a set of discrete or continuous domains D_1, \dots, D_n , X is a sequence of variables X_1, \dots, X_n and C is a set of m constraints in which can contain discrete constraints Γ , continuous constraints Φ or hybrid constraints Ω . A domain may be discrete domain or an interval and constraints are given as equalities or inequalities or conditional constraints or mixer constraints. The solution of a hybrid constraint network is:

$\Pi_{D,X,C} = \left\{ (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) \in X_1 \times X_2 \times \dots \times X_n : \bigwedge_{j=1}^m C_j(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) \right\}$ Here, the solution of a hybrid constraint network is a set of n -tuples, each tuple giving, for the n objects in X , a valuation which is acceptable to all the constraints in C . A hybrid constraint network is satisfiable if the network solution is not the empty set $\Pi_{D,X,C} \neq \emptyset$.

To solve for hybrid constraints in HCSPs, we need algorithms which combine good performance, obtainable correct results methods for continuous CSPs and discrete CSPs.

3. LOCAL CONSISTENCY PROBLEM

Local consistency is an important property in HCSP. In [3] considered propagate-algorithm computing local consistency (2-consistency), or in [5] integrated the local consistency methods for discrete and continuous constraints into a fix-point algorithm and it is achieved by specifying refine operators for each constraint type. In this section, we represent an algorithm which can solve local consistent for HCSP. The algorithm called HybridLocalLAI is built based on landmark.

The idea use Landmark-based Approximate Inference (LAI) method to solve for hybrid constraint satisfaction problems is proposed in this research. By the approach, we use approximate methods in mathematics to find landmarks for local consistent propagation and landmark partitions for global consistent propagation of HCSPs. The landmarks of each variable are obtained from constraint propagation helped the method solves not only local consistency but also global consistency solutions for HCSPs. The key of method is landmarks in domains of variables. Landmark is defined as follow:

Definition 5 (Landmarks) For a feasible domain of variable X , there exists interval I_A and I_B . Suppose I_B would be involved continuous solution, and I_A enclose with I_B . Any points p are in the interval I_B , which are fallen within interval space $p \in [B^L, \dots, B^U]$. If the following conditions are hold, the boundaries of interval I_B are called Landmarks $\{LM_n, LM_{n+1}\}$: S is a solution of variable X , $S \notin I_A \setminus I_B$, where $I_A \setminus I_B = \{x | (x \in I_A) \wedge (x \notin I_B)\}$. $I_B = \{LM_n, LM_{n+1}\}$, then $\{LM_n, LM_{n+1}\}$ are called landmarks.

In our method, the landmarks are found by using approximate mathematical tool, Newton's method, is integrated into the filtering algorithm for finding set of tolerating landmarks. During the refinement process, landmarks are local maximum, minimum and intersection points of constraints which are treated as finding solutions for $\frac{\partial f(X_1, \dots, X_n)}{\partial X_i} = 0$ with $f(X_1, \dots, X_n)$ are functions represent to constraints and X_1, \dots, X_n are objects in

constraint system. Through a landmark deduction procedure, we obtain a set of values in every variable domain for each constraint. These significant landmark points can be defined as:

Definition 6 Given a variable X , D is domain of X ($D = [L^B, U^B]$), the landmark point of X is a point p_i such that $L^B \leq p_i \leq U^B$, set of points $p_j : L^B \leq p_j \leq U^B, \forall_j$ called set of landmark points of X , if $p_i, p_j (i \neq j)$ are landmark points of X then $(p_i < p_j) \vee (p_i > p_j)$.

Each value in domain of discrete variables is treated as landmark-point in the landmark deduction procedure. We proposal an algorithm called HybridLocalLAI to solve local consistency and obtain set of landmark points in HCSP.

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HybridLocalLAI( $C, X, D$ )
1. for each hybrid constrain
    $C_i$  (may be  $\Gamma, \Phi$  or  $\Omega$ ) in  $C$  do
2.   for each variable  $X_i$  in  $C_i$  do
3.      $SL_i \leftarrow \phi$ 
4.     if  $(0 \in D_{X_i}) \&\& (X_i \in \Phi)$  then
5.        $SL_i \leftarrow SL_i \cup \{0\}$ 
6.     endif
7.     if  $X_i \in \Phi$  then
8.       while
          $(|x_{i,j+1} - x_{i,j}| > \varepsilon) \&\& (x_{i,j} \text{ located within } D_{X_i})$ 
       do
9.          $x_{i,j+1} = x_{i,j} - C_i / d(X_i)$ 
10.      endwhile
11.      if  $(x_{i,j} \text{ satisfy with } C_i) \&\& (x_{i,j} \notin SL_i)$  then
12.         $SL_i \leftarrow SL_i \cup x_{i,j}$ 
13.      endif
14.      else
15.        if  $(x_{i,j} \text{ satisfy with } C_i) \&\& (x_{i,j} \notin SL_i)$  then
16.           $SL_i \leftarrow SL_i \cup x_{i,j}$ 
17.        endif
18.      endif
19.    endfor
20.  endfor
21. for each variable  $X_i \in X$  do
22.   return  $D_{X_i}, SL_i$ 
23. endfor
24. end

```

Fig.1 Hybrid algorithm for local consistency HCSP.

Local propagation algorithm has computed a concise representation of potential solutions for a given hybrid constraint system and return sets of landmark-based of all variables in HCSP. The algorithm has reduced domains of variables by removing values which are infeasible with the constraints from domains. Therefore, reduced domains are represented by labels. Local propagation algorithm has used Newton's method as the approximate tool for the processing find landmark-based values of continuous variables. Filtering process will drop out landmark-based which are infeasible from domains and remained of domains will satisfy with the constraints in HCSP so output of the algorithm will obtain local consistency solutions.

We describe for the algorithm by a synthetic example about hybrid constraint system which has two hybrid constraints:

$$\begin{cases} \Omega_1 : bx^2 - y + 26(a-d) + 1 \leq 0 \\ \Omega_2 : -ax^2 + c - (y-6)^2 + 15b + 10 \leq 0 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

In this hybrid system, there are two continuous variables x, y with initial interval domain $x = [-5, 5]$, $y = [4, 9]$ and four discrete variables a, b, c, d with discrete initial domains $a = \{-15, 3, 70, -8, 19, 100\}$, $b = \{1, -6, 3, -9, 15, 10\}$, $c = \{-1, 800, -7, 1200, 9, 100\}$, $d = \{5, -20, 9, -160, 21, -42\}$. We have the graph to

represent the hybrid constraint network (1) in Fig. 2. The finding solution process, we obtain landmark points of variables: $x = [-2.82, -2.13, -0.75, 0.75, 2.13, 2.82]$, $y = [7.79, 9.00]$, $a = \{-15; 3; -8; 19\}$, $b = \{1; -6; 3; -9\}$, $c = \{-1; -7; 9; 100\}$, $d = \{5; 9; 21\}$ and from the landmark-based values of variables in HCSP, the HybridLocalLAI algorithm returns local consistency solution with narrower domains $x = [-2.82, 2.82]$, $y = [7.79, 9.00]$, $a = \{-15; 3; -8; 19\}$, $b = \{1; -6; 3; -9\}$, $c = \{-1; -7; 9; 100\}$, $d = \{5; 9; 21\}$. However, the results are local consistency and intermediate results that are used for the method finding global consistency.

Fig. 2 Graph represents hybrid constraint system (1)

4. GLOBAL CONSISTENCY PROBLEMS

The goal of global consistent of HCSP is to find interval solutions and values of continuous and discrete variables that satisfy all constraints in HCSP. The key idea of the method is to generalize local consistency criterion to a higher level where the set of all hybrid constraints is treated as a single global constraint. To compute the complete solution space of HCSPs, the propagation of all constraints can be represented by a set of landmarks of the feasible space. The set of landmarks are deduced in each domain of each variable of HCSP in during propagation finding local consistent and global consistent. The general framework of the proposed approach is an advanced reasoning algorithm, a consistent checking process that enforce on the local solution with new narrow domains and landmarks points. To isolate the continuous variables' domain by interval partitions in which including landmarks of local solution and consistent checking points as landmarks were yielded from local consistent propagation. Then each landmarks of domain will be checked and refined for global consistency by HybridGlobalLAI. Base on Newton's method, HybridLocalLAI and HybridGlobalLAI find the approximate solution on feasible landmark partitions in efficiency and quickly, it enforced a consistent checking process which is just considered for excluding the inconsistent space.

Definition 7 Given is a hybrid constraint network (D, X, C) , where D is a set of discrete and continuous domains D_1, \dots, D_n , X is a sequence of variables X_1, \dots, X_n and C is a set of m constraints in which can contain discrete constraints Γ , continuous constraints Φ and hybrid constraints Ω . The network is said to be globally consistent if

$$(\forall x_{i,0} \in C_i(X_i)) (\exists (x_{1,0}, \dots, x_{i,0}, \dots, x_{n,0}) \in C_1 \times \dots \times C_i \times \dots \times C_n) \left[\left((\forall C(x_{1,0}, \dots, x_{n,0})) \in C \right) \left(C(x_{1,0}, \dots, x_{n,0}) \text{ is satisfiable} \right) \right]$$

For any constraint C_j after using local filtering we get new domain for each variable, in which the domain is viewed as unions of sub-domains divided by consistent points. The sub-domains are used as interval landmarks and landmark points in propagation global consistency. With each landmark of domain will be checked and refined for global search by filtering function of HybridGlobalLAI. In refined iteration, if landmark is not consistent then it will be discarded from domain so the running time of global propagation will be reduced. The global consistency propagation performs as below: With hybrid constraint system (D, X, C) , the local consistent and landmark-based values of variables will be obtained by HybridLocalLAI algorithm, from the landmark-based values we will have partitions for global consistency process, after that we will assign in turn variables with in turn values in domain of variable $S_1 = \{X_1 = x_{1,1}, X_2 = x_{2,1}, \dots, X_n = x_{n,1}\}, \dots, S_m = \{X_1 = x_{1,k}, X_2 = x_{2,l}, \dots, X_n = x_{n,m}\}$.

When we get all tuple S_i and then the tuples S_i will be checked with all hybrid constraints in HCSP. The tuple S_i which satisfies with all constraints will be added into global consistency solution space of the HCSP. The process finding global conThe HybridGlobalLAI can be produced the global solution by the operator $\Psi^C = \Psi\left(\{p_{1,1}, \dots, p_{2,n}\}, \{p_{j,1}, \dots, p_{k,n}\}\right)$. Eventually, operator Ψ is newly applied to D such that: $\Psi(D) = \Psi\left(\{p_1, p_1^{h_1}\}, \{p_1^{h_1}, p_2\}, \{p_2, p_2^{h_2}\}, \{p_2^{h_2}, p_j\}, \{p_j, p_j^{h_j}\}, \{p_j^{h_j}, p_k\}\right)$ we obtained consistency solution will be stopped after all the tuples have been checked.

$$\Psi^C = \left\{ p_{1,1}, p_{1,2}, \dots, p_{1,m-1}, p_{1,m}^{h_1}, \{p_{1,1}, p_{1,2}, \dots, p_{2,n-1}, p_{2,n}\}, \right. \\ \left. \{p_{2,1}, \hat{p}_{2,2}, \dots, \hat{p}_{2,m-1}, \hat{p}_{2,m}^{h_2}\}, \{\hat{p}_{2,1}, \hat{p}_{2,2}, \dots, \hat{p}_{j,n-1}, p_{j,n}\}, \right. \\ \left. \dots, \{p_{j,1}, p_{j,2}, \dots, p_{j,m-1}, p_{j,m}^{h_j}\}, \{p_{j,1}, p_{j,2}, \dots, p_{k,n-1}, p_{k,n}\} \right\}$$

where p_x are assumptive remained which error $\delta < \varepsilon$, and \hat{p}_x are assumptive removed points which error $\delta > \varepsilon$ such that: $\Psi^C = \Psi\left(\{p_{1,1}, \dots, p_{1,m}^{h_1}\}, \{p_{1,1}^{h_1}, \dots, p_{2,2}\}, \{p_{2,1}\}, \{p_{j,n}\}, \{p_{j,1}, \dots, p_{j,m}^{h_j}\}, \{p_{j,1}^{h_j}, \dots, p_{k,n}\}\right)$

Since $p_{1,m}^{h_1} = p_{1,1}^{h_1}$, $p_{2,n} = p_{2,1}$, $p_{j,n} = p_{j,1}$, and $p_{j,m}^{h_j} = p_{j,1}^{h_j}$ which are contiguous to the domain, thus we union these isolated solution $\{p_{1,1}, \dots, p_{1,m}^{h_1}\}, \{p_{1,1}^{h_1}, \dots, p_{2,2}\}, \{p_{2,1}\}$ and $\{p_{j,n}\}, \{p_{j,1}, \dots, p_{j,m}^{h_j}\}, \{p_{j,1}^{h_j}, \dots, p_{k,n}\}$, such that the global solution is obtained by

$$\Psi^C = \Psi\left(\{p_{1,1}, \dots, p_{2,n}\}, \{p_{j,1}, \dots, p_{k,n}\}\right).$$

Return hybrid constraint system (1) example, we see that with approach landmark-based values, we can obtain not only local consistency but also global consistency for the constraint system. If we do not use landmark-based for process finding solution then we will obtain relaxed solution for $x = [-2.82, 2.82]$ and $y = [4, 9]$ for constraint system (1). However, among from -0.75^+ to 0.75^- is not satisfied the constraint for a reason of rigorous consistency and so the values of x, y are not global consistent for constraint system (1). The global solution space can be found by landmark-based values which are used for process finding global consistent solution. The key of method is landmarks in domains of variables which are remained to parts of refined domain by considering all constraints. There are so many points deduced during inference process, however, these points are meaningful and useful for finding solution in whole solving system. The final global consistent solution results are found with values of variables $x = [-2.82, -0.75] \cup [0.75, 2.82]$ and $y = [7.79, 9.00]$ which are shown in Fig 4. We use HybridGlobalLAI for the constraint system (1) and obtain the results in Table 1.

Table 1 The results of HybridGlobalLAI used for HCSP (1)

Var	Initial Domain	HybridGlobalLAI
x	$[-5, 5]$	$[-2.82, -0.75], [0.75, 2.82]$
y	$[4, 9]$	$[7.79, 9.00]$
a	$\{-15; 3; 70; -8; 19; 100\}$	$\{-15; 3; -8; 19\}$
b	$\{1; -6; 3; -9; 15; 10\}$	$\{1; -6; 3; -9\}$
c	$\{-1; 800; -7; 1200; 9; 100\}$	$\{-1; -7; 9; 100\}$
d	$\{5; -20; 9; -160; 21; -42\}$	$\{5; 9; 21\}$

HybridGlobalLAI(D, X, C)

1. $Q \leftarrow C_1, \dots, C_m$
2. $T \leftarrow \phi$
3. HybridPropagationLAI(D, X, C)
4. **for** each variable $X_i \in X$ **do**
 1. **if** $X_i \in$ continuous variables **then**
 2. $P_i \leftarrow$ {landmark points in SL_i divide domain into interval partitions}
 3. **else**
 4. $P_i \leftarrow SL_i$
 5. **endif**
 6. **endfor**
5. **for** each variable $X_i \in X$ **do**
 6. **for** each value $x_{i,j}$ in P_i **do**
 7. $S_k \leftarrow \{X_1 = x_{1,j}, \dots, X_n = x_{n,j}\}$
 8. **endfor**
 9. $T \leftarrow T \cup \{S_k\}$
 10. **endfor**
11. **while** ($Q \neq \phi$) **do**
 12. $C \leftarrow pop(Q)$
 13. **for** each $S_i \in S$ **do**
 14. **if** S_i unsatisfy C **then**
 15. $T \leftarrow T \setminus \{S_i\}$
 16. $Q \leftarrow C_1, \dots, C_m$
 17. **endif**
 18. **endfor**
 19. Delete C from Q
 20. **endwhile**
 21. **if** $T = \phi$ **then**
 22. *return* no global consistency
 23. **else**
 24. *return* T
 25. **endif**
 26. **end**

Fig. 3 Hybrid algorithm solve for global consistency

Fig. 4 Local consistency (a) and global consistency (b).

5. COMPLEXITY OF HYBRIDGLOBALLAI ALGORITHM

Complexity of our algorithm is estimated by the complexity of process for finding landmark-based values in local consistency propagation and complexity of process finding global consistency solutions. Sets of landmark-based values of variables are obtained by Newton's method and then the landmark-based values do not satisfy with constraints in HCSP will be deleted from domain to get local consistency. Therefore, the time complexity of process finding landmark-based values in local consistency propagation in the worst case is $O(m * n * \lg(\epsilon) * F(\epsilon))$, where n is number of variable, m is number of hybrid constraint in HCSP, $F(\epsilon)$ is cost of calculating $F(\Omega) / F'(\Omega)$ with ϵ -digit precision. On other words, the complexity of our method for local consistency is $O(n)$. Without taking advantage of landmark-based in constraint propagation, a search procedure would have to consider k^n assignments for n variables with k is number of values in domain and the complexity of search procedure for global consistency in the worst case is $O(m * n * k^n)$. However, with landmark-based the running time of process finding global consistency will be reduced because we never have to consider all values in domain. The complexity of our algorithm in the worst case will be

$$O(m * n * \lg(\epsilon) * F(\epsilon) + m * d^n) = O(d^n) \quad (2)$$

where d is the largest number in number of landmark-based of all variables. From expression (2), we see that the complexity of HybridGlobalLAI algorithm in the worst case is $O(d^n)$ and lower than the complexity of search procedure without using landmark-based for global consistency of HCSP $O(k^{n+1})$. We have d is the number of landmark-base and k is number of partitions in domains, by the algorithm then $d < k$, and $m, n, d, k \geq 1$, therefore, we have that $O(d^n) < O(k^{n+1})$. This means that our algorithm is better than search procedures without using landmark-based.

Fig. 5 Represent the complexity of other methods

In the Fig. 5, we have three demonstrations about the complexity of three methods: Landmark-based Approximate Inference which we propose to solve HCSP, Midpoint method which was used in [5] and 2K method used in [4] to solve global consistency solutions. We see that when the number of partitions of other methods increases then the complexity of the methods also increase. However, the increase of LAI method is slower than other methods, indications that LAI method solving for global consistent solution of CSP is better than Midpoint method and 2K method.

6. EXPERIMENTATION

Solving for Hybrid constraint systems based on numerical often get wrong results even for simple models such as the bouncing particle [2], we contend that landmark techniques guarantee the existence of a solution provide a

reliable framework for the problems by HybridLocalLAI and HybridGlobalLAI methods. There are several methods which have been proposed to solve for hybrid systems but they have problems with difficulties in numerical computation [6], [8], [10]. The methods output floating-point numbers that seem not to be completely incorrect, but there are some errors. More recently, some methods [2], [4] are proposed to solve HCSP which have different properties from the before methods. However, they also have some restrictions in performance such as only solving for specific type of constraints or only return local consistent of HCSPs. Our method with the landmark techniques has been used for some real work systems and we obtained the results which are not only local consistent but also global consistent. We use the hybrid system in [5] which will be tested by our method and we will show the results for testing the real application system: Industrial Mixer systems [5]. The problem system will be represented by hybrid constraint systems and has been described in [5] consists of configuring mixers used in industry. This system is very complex and described by discrete and continuous objects in constraints. The system can be presented as a hybrid constraint satisfaction problem, in which the relations of components or properties of components are constraints and variables in constraints are the components or properties. In Table 2 shows variables and the domain of variables in the system and the results local, global consistency solutions after we use HybridLocalLAI and HybridGlobalLAI algorithms for the hybrid constraint system. Moreover, the results were compared with Gelle's local consistency method [5]. From the comparison, we show that our method obtains not only local consistency results with interval values narrower than Gelle's method but also global consistency solution for the system.

7. CONCLUSIONS

We have introduced an efficient refinement algorithm which allows us to tackle constraint system without losing any solution for HCSPs. HybridGlobalLAI approach performs a global refinement on a constraint system, the principles presented here could be extended to other problems. The approach could play a role of global constraint for handling all equation constraints in many real-world applications where there exist numerous hybrid constraints.

We have compared our approach with corresponding refinement methods, the experiments show that the quality is comparable or even better in some cases; the strength is the low complexity and the ability to balance the workload. The methods have the following important aspects:

- i. Easy to implement: Based on the landmark technique, we can easily obtain the landmark points of continuous variables and discrete variables in HCSP and new narrower domains of variables from HybridLocalLAI procedure. The information will be used in HybridGlobalLAI to obtain global consistent for HCSP.
- ii. Efficiency improvement: The proposed approach tackles complicated problems with a low cost. The algorithm balances the work load and minimizes the number of operation with a low complexity.
- iii. Higher consistency level: The proposed approach can reach not only a local consistency, but also a global consistency for HCSP.
- iv. New efficiency approach to solve for HCSP: Local and global consistency are supported by refine landmark-based operators which are designed for hybrid constraint satisfaction problems. The propagation help to avoid searching all domains of variables, backtracking in order to obtain the complete solutions even the domains contain separate intervals in solution of continuous variables.

With the results of HybridGlobalLAI approach for real-world applications of HCSP, and on standard benchmark from the hybrid constraints. The algorithm has faster running time and returns correct results than other approaches, thus HybridGlobalLAI is more useful when the hybrid constraint system is very complicated with many continuous and discrete domains of the variables. Although the experimental results were obtained in a particular, we believe that HybridGlobalLAI approach can scale up to more complex and realistic problems, real-world applications.

Table 2. Representation local consistency solutions obtained from our method comparison with Gelle's method.

Variables	Initial Domains	Consistency Gelle's method	Local consistency our method	Global consistency our method
MT	{blending, entrainment, dispersion}	{blending, entrainment, dispersion}	{dispersion}	{dispersion}
MT.heattransfer	{true, false}	{false}	{false}	{false}
MT.slurrypressure	{low, high}	{low, high}	{low, high}	{high}
MT.slurryviscosity	{low, high}	{low, high}	{low, high}	{low}
MT.slurrydensity	[1, 2000]	[1, 2000]	[1, 2000]	[2, 2000]
M	{reactor, storagetank, mixer}	{storagetank, mixer}	{storagetank, mixer}	{mixer}
E.power	[0, 5000]	[0.2, 5000]	[0.2, 5000]	[0.827, 4999.722]
El.bottomArea	[0.01, 1000]	[0.01, 1000]	[0.01, 1000]	[0.01, 1000]
El.sradius	[0.01, 1000]	[0.01, 1000]	[0.803, 1.00]	[0.804, 1.000]
I.diameter	[0.1, 1000]	[0.4573, 6.9883]	[0.457, 0.658]	[0.529, 0.658]
I.entry	{top, side, center}	{top, side, center}	{top }	{top}
I.position	[0, 5]	[0, 5]	[5.00, 5.00]	[5.00, 5.00]
I.power	[0, 5000]	[0.1, 2500]	[0.2, 2500]	[0.413, 2499.86]
I.ratio	[0, 1]	[0, 1]	[0.329, 0.329]	[0.329, 0.329]
I.rps	[1, 100]	[1, 29.24]	[1, 1.265]	[1.000, 1.266]
V.diameter	[0.01, 1000]	[0.4817, 21.2344]	[1.607, 2.00]	[1.607, 2.00]
V.height	[0,1000]	[0.2408, 42.4688]	[3.215, 4.00]	[3.21, 4.00]
V.volume	[0.01, 1000]	[0.01, 150]	[4.22, 12.56]	[1.754, 2.00]
V	{cylindrical, elliptical, hemispherical}	{cylindrical, elliptical, hemispherical}	{cylindrical, hemispherical}	{ hemispherical}

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